

Influence of the temperature and alkalinity on biogas upgrading in algal-bacterial photobioreactors

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ABSTRACT

Biogas from the anaerobic digestion of organic waste is considered a renewable energy source for the production of heat and power due to its high CH₄ content. Biogas is mainly composed of CH₄ (40-75%), CO₂ (25-50%) and H₂S (0.005-2%). H₂S corrodes pipelines, storage tanks and reduces the lifetime of the combustion engines, while CO₂ reduces the specific calorific value of biogas and increases CO and hydrocarbon emissions (Toledo-Cervantes et al. 2016). In this context, the cost-effective removal of these biogas pollutants is necessary in order to comply with the technical specifications for its use as natural gas substitute. Physical/chemical or conventional biological technologies for CO₂ removal often need a previous H₂S cleaning step. On the other hand, processes such as water or chemical scrubbing and membrane separation, which allow for a simultaneous CO₂ and H₂S removal from biogas, exhibit prohibitive operation costs and pernicious environmental impacts. In this context, biogas upgrading in algal–bacterial photobioreactors constitutes a promising alternative for the removal of both biogas contaminants in a single-step process. This biotechnology is based on the photosynthetic CO₂ consumption by microalgae and the oxidation of H₂S to sulfate by sulfur-oxidizing bacteria using the oxygen photosynthetically produced. Previous studies focused on the optimization of operating parameter under constant laboratory conditions, which allowed obtaining a bio-methane with a composition complying with the specification of most European regulations. However, full-scale photobioreactors have to deal with the influence of diurnal and seasonal variations in temperature, which directly impacts on biomass growth kinetics and gas/liquid equilibria (Meier et al. 2017). In addition, the alkalinity of the cultivation broth (which itself depends on the alkalinity of the wastewater used to support the process: digestate or raw domestic wastewater) is another key operational parameter influencing CO₂ and H₂S mass transport from biogas (Posadas et al. 2017).

This work evaluated the influence of the temperature and inorganic carbon concentration in the cultivation broth on bio-methane quality using an indoors 180 L high rate algal pond (HRAP) interconnected to a settler prior to an absorption column (AC) via external recirculation of the settled cultivation broth (Figure 1). The system was operated under 12:12 h light:dark cycles at 1350 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹. During the illuminated period, the HRAP was fed with centrate as a nutrient source while synthetic biogas was sparged into the AC under co-current flow operation at a recycling liquid to biogas ratio (L/G) of 0.5 according to Toledo-Cervantes et al. (2017). Moreover, in order to compensate evaporation losses, tap water was supplied continuously. Four different operational conditions, characterized by inorganic carbon concentrations of 1700 mg IC/L and 500 mg IC/L (representatives of real digestates) at 15 and 35°C, were initially tested to optimize both parameters simultaneously. Moreover, two more operational conditions at 100 mg IC/L, typical IC concentrations of domestic

wastewater, at both temperatures are being studied. A constant biomass productivity of $7.5 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ was imposed throughout all the operational stages in absence of effluent. A complete H_2S removal and CO_2 -REs $> 98\%$ were obtained at 1700 mg IC/L regardless of the temperature. On the other hand, only CO_2 -REs about 50% and H_2S -REs $> 90\%$ were recorded at 500 mg IC/L , which highlighted the key role of alkalinity in this system. A low influence of the temperature was observed along the four stages.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the experimental set-up

CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, a biomethane quality complying with most European legislations for biogas use as a natural gas substitute was obtained at high alkalinities stages with a negligible effect of the temperature. A nearly complete removal of H_2S was found in all the stages.

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REFERENCES

- Meier L., Barros P., Torres A., Vílchez C. and Jeison D. (2017) Photosynthetic biogas upgrading using microalgae: effect of light/dark photoperiod. *Renewable Energy*. 106: 17-23
- Posadas E., Marín D., Blanco S., Lebrero R. and Muñoz R. (2017) Simultaneous biogas upgrading and centrate treatment in an outdoors pilot scale high rate algal pond. *Bioresour. Technol.*
- Toledo-Cervantes A., Serejo M., Blanco S., Pérez R., Lebrero R. and Muñoz R. (2016) Photosynthetic biogas upgrading to bio-methane: Boosting nutrient recovery via biomass productivity control. *Algal Res* 17: 46-52
- Toledo-Cervantes A., Madrid-Chirinos C., Cantera S., Lebrero R. and Muñoz R. (2017) Influence of the gas-liquid flow configuration in the absorption column on photosynthetic biogas upgrading in algal-bacterial photobioreactors. *Bioresour. Technol.* 225: 336-342.